

Compact System to Determine Single Yarn Strength and Elongation

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Abstract:

The two main properties of the majority of raw materials—whether they be metals or non-metals like foam, textiles, leather, paper, rubber, or completed goods like ropes, yarns etc which are tensile strength and elongation. These two characteristics frequently have a significant impact on whether any raw material is appropriate for a certain use [2]. Determining these attributes in a timely, easy, and accurate manner is therefore crucial.

A reasonably priced method for figuring out the tensile strength and elongation of cotton, jute, and silk yarn in a single strand is offered by the proposed model. They are based on the constant rate of traverse principle, which uses a motor, gear box, and screw arrangement to move the test specimen's opposite end at a predetermined speed while keeping the stationary end in a grasp. A load cell and a digital indicator are used to measure the load applied to the stationary grip. The digital indicator features a tare feature for employing different grips and a peak hold feature to indicate breaking load. The tester's frame is equipped with a linear scale that measures the elongation of the test specimen and marks the distance between the grips. The suggested approach is less expensive and more accurate.

Keywords: *Count lea strength product (CLSP), Constant Rate of Extension (CRE), Constant Rate of Loading (CRL), Constant Rate of Traverse (CRT), Gramm force (gf)*

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1. Introduction

The majority of basic materials, which may be metals or non-metals like plastic, foam, paper, rubber, textiles, leather or completed goods like rods, ropes, yarns, belts, etc., have tensile strength and elongation as their two main properties. When assessing whether any raw material is appropriate for a given application, these two characteristics frequently come into play [1]. Consequently, it is critical to quickly, easily, and properly ascertain these parameters.

The importance of yarn strength is to be studied from several aspects depending on its end use. The textile materials show marked differences in strength among themselves. There are many factors that are to be considered while estimating the yarn strength [3]. Yarns are used for manufacturing sewing threads and tough industrial fabrics. The end use of yarns depends upon the most important property, namely strength. The greatest force or load needed to break the material is known as the tensile property of a yarn. Because it directly affects the developed materials' strength, it is a metric that is crucial to the yarn-making process. Yarn strength is measured in a variety of ways.

The single yarn strength is measured in Newton (N) and centi-Newtons (cN) units. One Newton force is the amount of force needed by an object with a mass of one kilogram to accelerate it to one meter per Second Square. Information regarding the warping machine and loom efficiency can be obtained from the strength of a single yarn. The count lea strength product (CLSP) of the yarn is computed in order to determine its combined strength effect [4]. Using the wrapping reel, a Lea of 120 yards is formed, and the weight of the lea is computed to get the yarn count.

- i. **Types of Tensile Strength Testing Machines:** On the basis of the working principle, tensile strength testing machines can be categorized into three major categories.
- ii. **Constant Rate of Extension (CRE):** Here, the rate of elongation of the test specimen is kept constant and the load is applied accordingly. A constant rate of elongation is the basis for the Tensorapid-4's operation, which assesses a single yarn's tensile strength [4].
- iii. **Constant Rate of Loading (CRL):** The test sample is subjected to a load applied by the machines that increases with time. The specimen can freely extend, and for any given applied load, its extension will depend on its properties. This is the category in which the Lea Strength Machine operates [5].
- iv. **Constant Rate of Traverse (CRT):** This kind of apparatus uses two pulling clamps to measure the sample's tensile strength. A load measuring mechanism is activated by the second clamp, which applies the load while the first clamp travels at a constant speed.

Tensile strength is a crucial mechanical property of yarn that measures the maximum tensile or pulling force that a yarn can withstand without breaking [6]. It is a main parameter in determining the suitability of a yarn for various applications, such as textiles, sewing, knitting, or industrial uses. Tensile testing is a technique used to evaluate a yarn's toughness, elongation, and breaking force. So proposed technique use to obtain correct tensile strength in real time application in short time.

2. Yarn Strength and Elongation

The greatest force a yarn under tension may withstand before breaking is known as its yarn strength. This is dependent upon the fiber's resistance to slippage and strength. Yarn strength is particularly dependent on the fiber's properties (length, strength, and crimp), the yarn's evenness, particularly the presence of thin areas, and the yarn's construction parameters (count and twist) [5]. A yarn's extension, also known as its elongation, is the maximum length it can stretch before breaking. Frequently, it is stated as a percentage of the initial, or outstretched, length. There is a relationship between yarn strength and extension, which in spun yarns is mostly dictated by (a) the number of fibers in the yarn's cross-section, (b) the mean length of the fibers, and (c) the degree of twist that keeps the fibers together in the yarn. Extension and strength will increase in tandem with the degree of twist, until the yarn's strength actually begins to decline [6].

3. Methodology

The basic mechanism to measure yarn strength and elongation is shown in figure 1. As shown in figure 1 mechanism consists of load cell, upper jaw, lower jaw and helical drives from motor. Upper jaw is stationary where as lower jaw moves with motor. To measure yarn strength, lengths of yarn are broken by stretching yarn with lower jaw. Both the maximum breaking elongation and the maximum load are noted. The highest load expressed in gramme force (gf) or centiNewtons (cN). The % elongation at break is used to assess the maximum breaking extension.

Figure 1 - Basic mechanism [7]

With this mechanism proposed model provide a relatively inexpensive and compact model for estimate the elongation and tensile strength of cotton, jute, silk yarn in single strand [8].

Proposed method is based on the fixed rate of traverse concept, which involves holding first end of the specimen which we have to test in a stationary grip and using a motor, screw arrangement and gear box to move the other end at a predetermined speed.

Figure 2 - Block Diagram [9]

As shown in block diagram proposed system is mainly consisting of load cell, servo motor, and rotary encoder. Rotary encoder is mainly used to measure elongation.

3.1 Load Cell and HX711

A device that measures force or weight is called a load cell which is shown in figure 3. Load cell basically consist of strain gauge, which are tiny sensors that alter in electrical resistance in response to mechanical strain, are important to the operation of a load cell. One or more strain gauges are strategically positioned within the load cell to measure the deformation brought on by the applied force. It is frequently utilized in many commercial and industrial applications, including force measurement devices, material testing apparatuses, and weighing scales. The exerted force is transformed into a measurable and interpretable electrical signal by the load cell. Piezo-resistivity is the basis for the operation of resistive load cells [10].The resistance of the sensor changes as a load is applied to it. When an input voltage is applied, this resistance change causes an output voltage change. An elastic component with several strain gauges attached is used to create a load cell. As can be seen in Figure 3, the load cell is made up of four strain gauges in total, which are attached to both the upper and bottom surfaces.

Figure 3 - Load Cell

The elastic portion of a resistive load cell deflects as indicated and produces strain at those areas as a result of the stress exerted when the load is applied to the cell's body as shown below. Consequently, as figure 4 illustrates, two strain gauges are in compression and the remaining two are in tension.

Figure 4 - Load Cell with elastic deformation

Elastic deformation occurs in the load cell due to weight acting on its metal spring element during a measurement. Strain gauges (SG), fixed to the spring element, and transform this strain positive or negative into an electrical output. This change in strain or resistance is converted into voltage that is proportionate to the load using a Wheatstone bridge circuit [11]. An electrical part that is frequently used with load cells to interface them with microcontrollers is the HX711 module shown in figure 5. It functions as an analog-to-digital converter made especially for load cell uses.

Figure 5 - HX711 Pin out

As per specification of HX711 is concern output Sensitivity is $1.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ mV / V}$, two selectable differential input Channels, On-chip power-on-reset, measurement Resolution is 24 bit and on-chip active low noise PGA with the selectable gain of 32, 64 and 128. Load cell is connected to the HX711 module's input terminals and the module is connected to a microcontroller using standard communication protocols such as I2C. Because load cells are small, it is simple to incorporate them into various structures or systems. They can be applied in a number of sectors, including agriculture, industry, transportation, and healthcare. The purpose of load cells is to endure severe conditions and frequent loading [12]. Usually composed of sturdy materials like aluminum or stainless steel, they are long-lasting and durable. Installing and connecting load cells to measurement systems is simple. They can be easily integrated into pre-existing systems because they frequently feature standardized mounting holes or connectors.

3.2 Microcontroller

In proposed model we use ATmega328P microcontroller. The ATmega328P is an 8-bit AVR microcontroller with great performance and low power consumption. It has advanced RISC architecture. ATmega328P has program memory size 32KB.SRAM with 2KB. It has CPU speed of 20MIPS. ATmega328P has data EPROM with 1KB.This microcontroller also has 3 timer with capture, compare and PWM model. Atmega328 support different communication protocol like UART,SPI and I2C. This controller has two SPI port.

Figure 6 - ATmega 328 microcontroller

3.3 Rotary Encoder

A rotary encoder, also called a shaft encoder, is an electro-mechanical device that converts the angular position or motion of a shaft or axle into analog or digital output signals. It is depicted in figure 7. There are two main types of rotary encoders: absolute and incremental. An absolute encoder serves as an angle transducer since its output shows the shaft's present position [13]. Information about the motion of the shaft is obtained from the incremental encoder's output and is usually processed into position, speed, and distance data. The rotary encoder has five pins. The first pin is GND, second is VCC with positive supply voltage, typically between 3.3 and 5 volts. The third pin SW is the output of the push button switch (active low). The fourth and fifth pins are DT (Output B) and CLK (Output A) resp. DT (Output B) is similar to CLK output, but it lags behind CLK by a 90° phase shift. This output is used to determine the direction of rotation.CLK (Output A) is the primary output pulse used to determine the amount of rotation. Each time the knob is turned in either direction by just one detent (click), the 'CLK' output goes through one cycle of going HIGH and then LOW.

Figure 7 - Rotary Encoder

Applications for rotary encoders include industrial controls, robotics, photographic lenses, and computer based devices like op to-mechanical mice, controlled stress rheometers and trackballs and many more. These encoders are used in a wide range of mechanical system monitoring and control applications. As seen in figure 8, the encoder consists of a disk with uniformly spaced contact zones connected to two distinct contact pins, A and B, as well as the common pin C.

Figure 8 - Encoder Disk Structure

Pins A and B will begin to make contact with the common pin when the disk begins to rotate gradually, at which point the two square wave output signals will be created appropriately. If we simply count the signal's pulses, we may utilize any of the two outputs to get the rotational position. Nonetheless, we must take into account both signals simultaneously if we wish to ascertain the direction of rotation as well.

Figure 9 - Output signal from Pin A and B

Figure 10 - Schematic of Proposed Model

Two output signals are 90 degrees out of phase from one another, as seen in figure 9. When the encoder rotates in a clockwise direction, output A will occur before output B. Thus, we may observe that the two output signals have different values at that point if we count the steps every time the signal changes, either from High to Low or from Low to High. Conversely, when the encoder rotates in a counterclockwise direction, the output signals exhibit identical values. In light of this, we can easily program our controller to read the rotation direction and encoder location. Figure 10 show schematic of proposed model consists of display section and actual mechanism.

4. Result & Analysis

We perform different experiment to find out the single yarn strength and elongation percentage at break of the given sample of cotton single yarn by using proposed model. Strength of single yarn is a ratio of breaking load in gram and count of yarn in Tex. The particular test length of the specimen is fixed in between the two gripper. The length of the specimen is taken as 60cm. The extra material is cut off exactly at the clamp position. When the machine is started the lower grip travels downward and tension develop in the specimen. Microcontroller detects breaking point with the help of load cell. Encoder attached with servo motor to estimate elongation. This process is repeated with 10 of these specimens, to estimate elongation percentage and single yarn strength in gms/Tex shown in table1.The yarn count determined by the beesley balance was known before to the experiment. Mean value of tenacity from table 1 is 11.26 gm/Tex.

Table 1 - Single Yarn Strength with count in Tex =22.28 T

Number of Observation	Test Length	Breaking load in gms	Tenacity in gm/Tex
1	60cm	232	10.41
2	60cm	251	11.26
3	60cm	263	11.80
4	60cm	243	10.91
5	60cm	263	11.80
6	60cm	234	10.50
7	60cm	272	12.21
8	60cm	243	10.91
9	60cm	253	11.36
10	60cm	233	11.46

At the time of conducting above experiment we also estimate elongation. With the help of rotary encoder and circumference of lower jaw microcontroller estimated elongation which is shown in table 2. Table2 also shows elongation in percentages. Mean elongation percentages is 3.72.

Table2 - Single Yarn Elongation with count in Tex=22.28 T

Number of Observation	Test Length	Elongation in cm	Elongation Percentage
1	60cm	2.2	3.67
2	60cm	2.1	3.50
3	60cm	1.8	3.00
4	60cm	1.9	3.17
5	60cm	2.7	4.50
6	60cm	2.5	4.17
7	60cm	2.2	3.67
8	60cm	2.1	3.50
9	60cm	2.5	4.17
10	60cm	2.3	3.83

5. Conclusion

Proposed model is simple in design. This model has high efficiency and accuracy. Also this system provides smooth performance. Textile professionals can test any type of roving made up of varying percentages of fibers using the developed model. As previously said, the experts can use the offered model to determine the yarn strength without having to physically handle the data. The parameters in the proposed model are those that technicians typically measure before beginning the spinning process. They can thus test a lot of ravings quickly till they find the ideal desired strength attribute.

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